

ANALYSIS OF THE CONTENT OF PRIMARY EDUCATION TEXTBOOKS "MOTHER LANGUAGE"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19255136>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23rd March 2026

Accepted: 25th March 2026

Online: 27th March 2026

KEYWORDS

primary education, native language textbooks, content, didactic analysis, educational material, speech skills, educational standard, methodological approach, educational tasks, quality of education

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the content of primary education textbooks "Mother Tongue" from a pedagogical and methodological perspective. The consistency of the topics presented in the textbooks, the suitability of educational materials for the age characteristics, their role in the development of speech skills, and their compliance with educational standards are studied. The system of tasks in the textbooks and their importance in the formation of independent thinking, listening comprehension, reading and writing skills in students are also highlighted. As a result of the analysis, existing shortcomings were identified and scientific and methodological recommendations were developed to improve the content of the textbooks.

The development of society is directly related to the development and progress of science and technology, education and the mother tongue. At the lower stages of the initial education and mother tongue processes, the processes of teaching and teaching the mother tongue to the student, as well as the tasks and textbooks, were organized in the form of very simple requirements and processes, but in today's era of advanced science and technology, the educational process is becoming more complex, because one of the main problems is to interest today's students and organize an effective educational process for them. Therefore, the scope of the educational system, which is developing along with social life and development, is also expanding. Naturally, the above situation is reflected in school textbooks. Mother tongue textbooks are no exception to this situation. If we pay attention to our initial mother tongue textbooks, you can see that more attention is paid to grammar and the student's written literacy. With the development of information technologies and the introduction of modern teaching methods, the content of our textbooks has also been updated. There have been major changes in assignments and exercises. In particular, the scope of assignments and exercises has expanded. Today's textbooks, based on the content of education, are aimed at raising a student who thinks freely in all areas of life, finds a way out in any situation, and can express his or her thoughts fluently in writing and orally. Mother tongue textbooks have also taken on a new look in accordance with the same content. Special attention is paid to the listening comprehension skills that help students respect and listen to the opinions of others, and express their opinions correctly through direct listening. The 4th grade "Mother Tongue" textbook was published in 2024 with a new content. It does not

contain audio texts and learning tasks that develop listening comprehension skills. This is also the case with the 3rd grade “Mother Language” textbook published in 2020.

While language teaching around the world is based on speaking competence, these textbooks, originally created for primary school, are now adapted to grammatical education.

In primary school native language textbooks, there are tasks aimed at developing listening comprehension skills, which are mainly focused on listening to the text, understanding its content and retelling it. These tasks play an important role in forming students' ability to perceive and understand information through hearing. However, an analysis of their content and methodological aspects also reveals some shortcomings.

First of all, most of the tasks given in textbooks are organized in the form of listening to the text and answering questions. These tasks help students understand the main content, but are often limited to checking superficial knowledge. That is, the student repeats specific facts taken from the text, but does not reach the level of in-depth analysis or drawing conclusions.

Secondly, retelling tasks are widely used. These tasks develop students' memorization and speech reconstruction skills, but they do not sufficiently stimulate creative and critical thinking. The student gets used to repeating what he has heard more often.

Thirdly, in some tasks, pre- and post-listening activities are not sufficiently organized. For example, before listening to the text, students are not asked questions that arouse interest, or after listening, there is little reinforcement with analytical and problem-based tasks.

Also, the tasks in the textbooks are not sufficiently interactive and have a differentiated approach. As a result of giving all students the same tasks, their individual capabilities are not taken into account. This leads to some students not actively participating.

However, there are also positive aspects. Through some tasks, students acquire skills such as distinguishing the main idea from the text, evaluating characters, and reacting to events. These are important components of listening comprehension.

In general, although there are tasks in native language textbooks that develop listening comprehension skills, they need to be improved methodologically. In particular, by enriching tasks in a problematic, analytical and creative direction, introducing a step-by-step approach and taking into account the individual characteristics of students, listening comprehension skills can be developed more effectively.

Tasks on the formation of listening comprehension skills play an important role in native language textbooks for primary school students. Because listening comprehension develops the ability to perceive oral speech, distinguish meaning, understand the main idea and express reactions to the text heard.

1.-2-Table

Topshiriq turi	Mazmuni	Kuchli jihatlari	Kamchiliklari	Takomillashtirish yo'llari
Matnni tinglab savollarga javob berish	O'qituvchi o'qigan matn asosida savollarga javob berish	Asosiy mazmunni tushunishga yordam beradi	Yuzaki tushunish bilan cheklanadi	Tahliliy va muammoli savollarni ko'paytirish
Qayta hikoya qilish	Eshirilgan matnni og'zaki qayta bayon	Nutq va xotirani rivojlantiradi	Kreativ fikrlashni kam rivojlantiradi	Ijodiy qayta hikoya (yakunni o'zgartirish) kiritish

	qilish			
Asosiy fikrni aniqlash	Matndan asosiy g'oyani topish	Mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantiradi	Har doim chuqur tahlil talab qilmaydi	Sabab-oqibatli savollar bilan boyitish
Qahramonlarga baho berish	Matndagi obrazlarga munosabat bildirish	Baholash ko'nikmasini rivojlantiradi	Ba'zan umumiy javoblar bilan cheklanadi	Dalillash talab qilinadigan topshiriqlar berish
Tinglashdan keyingi savollar	Matn yuzasidan umumiy savollar	Mazmuni mustahkamlaydi	Bosqichliligi yetarli emas	Oldin-jarayon-keyin tizimini joriy etish
Interaktiv topshiriqlar (kam uchraydi)	Rolli o'yin, dialoglar	Faollikni oshiradi	Yetarli darajada qo'llanilmaydi	Interfaol metodlarni keng joriy etish

Listening comprehension tasks are divided into the following types according to their content:

Topshiriq turi	Maqsadi	Misol (3-4-sinf darsligidan)	Tahlil
1. Axborotni aniqlash topshiriqlari	Eshitilgan matndan fakt, ism-sharif, joy nomlarini eslab qolish	"O'qituvchi matnni o'qib beradi. O'quvchilar matndan shahar nomlarini sanab o'tadilar."	Bu turdagi topshiriq o'quvchining diqqatini jamlash va axborotni selektiv qabul qilish malakasini rivojlantiradi.
2. Asosiy mazmuni aniqlash topshiriqlari	Matnning bosh g'oyasini tushunish, umumlashtirish	"Matnni tinglang va uning nima haqida ekanligini bitta gap bilan ayting."	Ushbu topshiriq o'quvchilarda mantiqiy eshitish, tahliliy fikrlash hamda fikrni umumlashtirish ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi.
3. Eshitilgan matn bo'yicha savol-javob	Matn mazmunini qayta ishlash, faol tinglovchi sifatida ishtirok etish	"Matnda qahramon nima uchun shunday yo'l tutdi?"	Bu topshiriq og'zaki nutqni faollashtiradi , o'quvchini tushunganini so'z bilan ifodalashga o'rgatadi.
4. Kutilmagan yakunli matnlar asosidagi topshiriqlar	Matn davomida taxmin qilish, natijani oldindan aytish	"Hikoya oxirida nima bo'lishi mumkin deb o'ylaysiz?"	O'quvchilarning ijodiy va taxminiy fikrlashini, emotsional idrokini rivojlantiradi.
5. Eshitilgan matn asosida rasm chizish yoki jadval to'ldirish	Matnni vizual idrok bilan bog'lash	"Matnda aytilgan voqealar ketma-ketligini rasmlar orqali tasvirlang."	Bu topshiriq multimodal idrokni kuchaytiradi va tinglab eslab qolishni samarali qiladi.

Practical observations

For example, in exercise 57 of the 3rd grade Native Language textbook, the following task is given:

"The teacher will read the text expressively. Listen and determine the qualities of the hero of the text."

This task requires the listening student not only to hear the text, but also to perceive the moral conclusion reflected in it. This develops the level of emotional, moral and spiritual understanding in the student.

Listening comprehension tasks in the Native Language textbook:

- develop students' listening attention, logical perception, and content analysis;
- strengthen oral speech, thinking, and creativity skills;
- serve to form communicative competence.

However, the analysis shows that in some textbooks, listening comprehension tasks are short or passive in nature, and it is necessary to organize them in more interactive, multi-stage forms.

Analysis of listening comprehension tasks in the 2nd grade “Mother Language” textbook

Listening comprehension tasks in the 2nd grade are mainly organized in the form of listening carefully to short texts, identifying the main idea, and answering questions. At this stage, children develop the skills of distinguishing sounds, remembering words and sentences, and perceiving oral text.

Topshiriq namunasi	Maqsadi	Tahlil
“Matni tinglang va unda kim haqida so‘z yuritilganini ayting.”	Eshitilgan matn mazmunini tushunish	Bolada eshitish diqqatini rivojlantiradi, asosiy fikrni ajratish ko‘nikmasi shakllanadi.
“Matndan sizga yoqqan joyni ayting.”	Shaxsiy munosabat bildirish	O‘quvchi matni faqat eshitmay, unga emotsional javob beradi.
“O‘qituvchi she‘rni o‘qiydi. Qaysi so‘zlar takrorlanmoqda?”	Fonetik e‘tibor va so‘z eslab qolish	Takror orqali tovush idroki, fonematik eshitish mustahkamlanadi.

Listening comprehension tasks in the 2nd grade textbook serve to increase students' attention, auditory memory, and vocabulary. However, they need to be enriched with tasks in the form of demonstrations or games.

Analysis of listening comprehension tasks in the 3rd grade “Mother Language” textbook
 General description

In the 3rd grade, texts become larger in size and their content complexity increases. Students are required not only to listen, but also to analyze the text and draw logical conclusions.

Topshiriq namunasi	Maqsadi	Tahlil
“Matni tinglang. Uning asosiy g‘oyasini bitta gap bilan ifoda eting.”	Umumlashtirish, asosiy mazmunni tushunish	O‘quvchilarda mantiqiy fikrlashni faollashtiradi.
“Matndan qahramonning qanday fazilatlarini bilib oldingiz?”	Axloqiy tushunishni rivojlantirish	O‘quvchi eshitilgan matndan shaxsiy xulosa chiqaradi.
“Matni tinglang va voqealar ketma-ketligini sanang.”	Strukturaviy idrokni shakllantirish	Bolalar voqealarni eshitish asosida ketma-ket joylashtirishni o‘rganadi.

Listening comprehension tasks in grade 3 are aimed at analyzing content, understanding logical sequences, and developing verbal thinking. However, the criteria for their evaluation are not clearly defined, so it would be useful to introduce a rating or point system.

Listening comprehension tasks in grade 4 develop students' skills in independent analysis, expressing personal attitudes, and drawing ideological conclusions. The texts are more artistic and moral in nature.

Topshiriq namunasi	Maqsadi	Tahlil
“Matni tinglang. Undan qanday saboq olish mumkin?”	Ma’naviy xulosa chiqarish	O’quvchi eshitilgan matndan axloqiy g’oya ajratadi.
“Matnda qahramon qanday qaror qabul qildi? Siz bo’lsangiz nima qilardingiz?”	Mustaqil fikrlashni rag’batlantirish	O’quvchi eshitgan voqeani hayotiy tajribasi bilan solishtiradi.
“Matn asosida kichik og’zaki hikoya tuzing.”	Og’zaki nutqni rivojlantirish	Tinglab tushunish natijasida o’quvchi matnni qayta yaratish orqali nutqiy faol bo’ladi.

Listening comprehension tasks in the 4th grade textbook serve to develop students' critical thinking, expressive speech, and spiritual awareness. At the same time, enriching the tasks with audio recordings, videos, and dramatization techniques increases their effectiveness.

General conclusions

Sinf	Asosiy yo’nalish	O’sish dinamikasi
2-sinf	Diqqat, eshituv xotirasi, so’zlarni farqlash	Boshlang’ich bosqich, asosiy malaka shakllanadi
3-sinf	Mantiqiy idrok, tahliliy fikrlash	Mazmuniy tahlil bosqichi
4-sinf	Tanqidiy fikrlash, ma’naviy xulosa chiqarish	Mustaqil nutqiy faoliyat bosqichi

With the exception of upper-grade mother tongue textbooks, they focus on developing listening comprehension skills.

The teacher's book, i.e. the methodological manual developed in 2020, explains the listening comprehension competency as follows: "It is important to practice listening comprehension skills in native language lessons. Through this process, the student's ability to maintain attention for a long time, the ability to understand the oral thoughts of others, monological and dialogical speech, and the content of the text are formed. Students should be able to understand scientific and popular speech in the field, distinguish the main information in the listened text, perceive the content and purpose of current information in the media, understand it by listening, understand the correctness, logical consistency, purity, and impact of speech, and distinguish and understand the meaning of stable terms and professional words. Through these ideas, the ability to listen to and understand is also recognized as one of the important competencies, and exercises and exercises are provided to develop skills in students. tasks have been given. Based on the above definition, the following results are expected from the primary school native language lesson:

Listening comprehension:

- can listen and understand monological, dialogical speech and conversation;
- understands the listened text (audio text, narrative text);
- understands the main information, events in the watched video;
- listens and understands the grammatical principles and information given in the

textbook;

- understands, compares, separates, summarizes and concludes the necessary details, ideas from the information in various simple texts and tables;
- listens to audio material, tells it orally and writes it down in text form;

This result is expected from the tasks given in the textbook, but we can see that the tasks are not at the required level. It is in the 1st-4th grade native language textbooks that listening comprehension tasks have been included starting from the 2020 edition given, but the absence of audio podcasts of the given tasks indicates that the listening comprehension tasks are not fully formed. All tasks in this area are given in text form. There are a total of 19 listening comprehension tasks in the textbook in text form, but they are called listen. The condition of the task is set in the form of listen. No audio podcast is given for listening. The conditions are created for the student to read the text directly on his own. Such a task mainly corresponds to the reading comprehension competency. It would be appropriate if the audio were given for the listening comprehension task and the text were cited as a reference on the last pages of the book. For example, on page 9 of the textbook, the following learning task is given:

Exercise 6. What does the poet want to say through these lines? Explain your thoughts.

Sen dilda qo'shiqsan, elga nur madhing,

O'zbegin, o'zligim, hayotim, borim.

Jahonga namoyon qudrat-u ko'rking,

Turkiy el so'zligim, ona diyorim,

Yerlari muqaddas O'zbekistonsan.

Nazarmat Egamnazarov¹

This task is not given in text form and the audio version for listening is not given anywhere. Students get acquainted with the finished text at once, and the results that the teacher intended and noted above cannot be fully achieved from the tasks given for listening comprehension. In general, the 4th grade native language textbook does not provide separate tasks for listening comprehension. True, this text can be read and listened to by the teacher or a fluent student, but if it is used with audio tools and podcasts, the intended result would be achieved. We can see that all the tasks included in the 5th grade native language textbook are formulated in the same way. However, we can admit that the text was chosen very well in terms of didactic-native language and taking into account the age of the student. The above task was one of the first tasks of the native language textbook. Now let's turn our attention to the tasks on the last pages and topics. On page 118 of the book, the task on the topic "Lesson 76. Working on the text and vocabulary" is presented in the form of "Listen to the story."

¹ M.E.Toirova Ona tili: Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 4-sinfi uchun darslik, I qism. / M.E.Toirova - Toshkent: "Novda Edutainment", 2023. - 88 b.

Yomg'irli kunda raqsga tushishni yaxshi ko'radigan yosh, jajji bir tovu bor edi. U bog'da gullarga mahliyo bo'lib, qo'shiqlar aytardi. Nima qilsa ham unga qo'pol tovushi o'z kamchiliklarini eslataverardi. Tovus yaqin atrofda sayrayotgan bulbulning yoqimli, mayin xonish (sayrash)ini eshitar va har safar uning ko'zlari alamdand yoshga to'lardi.

U nima uchun bunday ahvolga tushayotganiga hayron bo'la boshladi. Shu chog' qo'lga bir bog' o't bilan bog' egasi paydo bo'ldi va tovuuga murojaat qildi:

- Nega xafasan, ko'nglingni chog' qilish uchun mana bu giyohlarni senga hadya qilaymi?

- Bulbulning shunday chiroyli ovozi bor. Sayrashda men undan o'ta olmayman. Nima uchun u menda yo'q? - dedi tovu.

- Ha, bulbulning shirali, xush ovozi bor. Lekin sen ham chiroyli va yorqin patlar bilansiylangansan! Hammasi buni qanday qabul qilishingda va undan qanday foydalanishingdadir.

Ovu o'zini boshqa qushlarga qiyoslay boshladi. O'zidagi ne'matning noyobligini tushunib yetdi. ("Qisqa hikoyalar"dan)

This task is also given as "listen" but is included in the textbook in text form. If the task was given in audio form, and students listened to this task and tried to find similar and meaningful words in the text, the task would be even more interesting for students and serve as a means of developing their concentration. If we pay attention to the two tasks above, although they are different in content, their similarity in form is striking. We can note that almost all the tasks in the book are in this form. Gradually, our textbooks are being developed in a similar way to textbooks in developed countries, but there are still shortcomings. Although not in the primary grades, there are listening comprehension exercises starting from the 5th grade. When developing a native language textbook, each topic should be enriched with all elements of speech competence. If we pay attention to English textbooks, which are specifically developed in terms of teaching, all types of speech competence are found in each topic in all textbooks and in all topics included in the textbook. We see that the form of assignments is also different. In the 5th grade native language textbook, all assignments have the same form, which creates boredom in the student and leads to a decrease in interest in learning. It would be convenient for both the student and the teacher to develop high-quality audios for each listening comprehension competency and provide them with QR codes under or before the assignment. In cases where there are many forms of assignments, it is necessary to develop audios recorded on separate discs for each grade textbook. In order to provide effective education to children, we must first of all pay attention to the full formation of material conditions. To do this, fully equip each classroom technically, paying special attention to the number of students. In the case of a large number of students, it is necessary to teach the mother tongue lessons separately, like foreign language or Russian language subjects. Only then can we work with all students individually and achieve effective education. This highlights the need to revise the mother tongue textbooks in a systematic manner, without neglecting grammar, in order to incorporate all elements of speech competence in the topics. If we say that there are no tasks on listening comprehension in the new 5th grade mother tongue textbook, we can see that among the tasks in the topics there is a task in the form of "listen to the text", and in the methodical manual specially developed for teachers, information is included about the listening comprehension competence and its intended

purpose. To solve this problem, it is necessary to change the word “listen” in the textbook to “read the text”, and it is necessary to remove the sentences in the methodical manual about the concept of listening comprehension competence, its purpose, and expected results. Or it is necessary to develop audio options for each task. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the approach and approach to the form and structure of tasks, more serious work should be done on new textbooks, and when working on these textbooks, special attention should be paid to the structure of listening comprehension competence: form and content, and the need to diversify the form of tasks will further increase the quality and level of interest of textbooks.

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